

Sant'Anna

School of Advanced Studies – Pisa

**PH.D. AGROBIOSCIENCES
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"Studying new polymicrobial inoculants to improve herbaceous and arboreal plants' quality"

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- Research Scholarship at Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna: Development of innovative protocols for Olive (*Olea europaea* L.) agamic propagation to preserve agronomically important cultivars
- DnD Biotech: R&D in the field of biostimulants, strengtheners, and soil-improvers products for agriculture
- MSc in Plants and Microbial Biotechnologies, University of Pisa, Italy: Efficacy of *Trichoderma gamsii* T6085 against fungi of the genus *Fusarium*, agents of FHB in wheat.
- BSc in Biological Sciences, University of Pisa, Italy.

Abiotic stresses caused by climate change

Abuse/incorrect use of agrochemicals

**Water scarcity
and soil
salinity stress**

**Harm human
and animal
health**

**Reduce
ecosystem's
biodiversity**

**Soil and
groundwater
pollution**

Ruano-rosa et al., (2017); Adesemoye et al., (2009)

Microbial biostimulants and biofertilizers

- ▲ improves plant nutrition, growth, productivity and stress tolerance
- ▲ effective on different crops
- ▲ no pollution, no harm to people/animals' health and to biodiversity

- ▲ develop more cutting-edge and efficient solutions ▲
- ▲ polymicrobial formulations containing a heterogeneous mixture of beneficial microorganisms with multiple functionalities ▲

Sangiorgio et al., (2020), Castiglione et al., (2021); Ganugi et al., (2021) ; Colla & Roupael, (2015); Bashan & de-Bashan, (2010); Bartolini et al., (2017); Toffanin et al., (2016)

Aim of the work

Select novel microbial combination of agro-biotechnological interest

Deepen the knowledge about the PGP abilities of the involved microorganism

The project

Experiments will be about:

Preliminary studies

Roots/tissues colonization ability

Improvement of root architecture development

Nitrogen fixation

Involved
Microorganisms

Azospirillum sp.,
Bacillus sp.,
Methylobacterium sp.,
Trichoderma sp.

Phytohormones, NO
producers, N fixers, P
solubilization, siderophores
producers

Preliminary studies

- ▲ Bibliographic research
- ▲ Microbial *in vitro* analyses (best growth medium and growth conditions, compatibility, phytohormones production, ability to fix N, solubilize P, produce siderophores, produce NO)

Roots/tissues colonization ability

- ▶ Tomato seeds and olive semi-hardwood cuttings
- ▶ Growth chamber
- ▶ *Azospirillum* sp., *Bacillus* sp., *Trichoderma* sp., alone and mixed
- ▶ Tissues and rhizosphere: Histological assays + molecular assays (RT-PCR)

Improvement of root architecture development

- ▶ Tomato seeds and olive semi-hardwood cuttings
- ▶ Growth chamber + special olive propagation station
- ▶ Cuttings belonging to cultivars and clones with different rhizogenic ability
- ▶ *Azospirillum* sp., *Bacillus* sp., *Trichoderma* sp., alone and mixed
- ▶ Histological assays + biochemical assays (i.e. polyphenol oxidase and peroxidase activity)
- ▶ Biomass analysis, stem length and number of primary and adventitious roots

Low nitrogen input

- ▲ Adult tomato plants and young olive trees
- ▲ Green house + field condition
- ▲ *Azospirillum* sp., *Methylobacterium* sp., alone and mixed, synthetic N, bacteria + N
- ▲ Histological assays to assess microbial presence in the tissues
- ▲ Nitrate reductase (NR) activity, plant morphology, biomass analysis, antioxidant, phenols, pH and total soluble sugar content

Expected Results

**Select novel microbial combination
of agro-biotechnological interest**

**Deepen the knowledge about the PGP
abilities of the involved microorganism**

**New protocols to be
applied at nursery level**

**Methodological proposal to
verify the effectiveness of a
product in a short time**

Time schedule

Activity	1° year				2° year				3° year				
Preliminary analyses	Autumn	Winter	Spring										
Roots/tissues colonization ability		Winter	Spring	Summer	Autumn								
Improvement of root architecture development		Winter	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter	Spring	Summer	
Low nitrogen input trials		Winter	Spring	Summer		Winter	Spring	Summer		Winter	Spring	Summer	
Report/thesis			Spring	Summer			Spring	Summer		Winter	Spring	Summer	

Autumn	
Winter	
Spring	
Summer	

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References

Picture by Maria Orlova - Pexels: <https://www.pexels.com/it-it/foto/ramo-di-ulivo-in-giardino-buio-4916275/>

Picture by ROMAN ODINTSOV - Pexels: <https://www.pexels.com/it-it/foto/rami-frutta-olive-foglie-verdi-5319464/>

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**Thank you for
your attention**

